

Greenhouse evaluation of granular, wettable powder, and flowable insecticide formulations for tungro prevention

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Some insecticides appear to prevent tungro infection in addition to killing the green leafhopper vector *Nephotettix virescens*. Greenhouse trials evaluated three insecticide formulations (see table). Three replications of 20 35-day-old Taichung Native 1 plants planted in 50- × 50- × 10-cm galvanized trays were tested. Granular insecticides (2 kg ai/ ha) were broadcast on the soil surface. Wettable powder and flowable insecticides (0.1% concentration) were sprayed on plants. At 1 and 5 days after treatment

(DAT) each plant was inoculated with 2 viruliferous *N. virescens*. An equal number of untreated plants were inoculated as a check. Insect mortality was recorded 48 hours after caging, and infected plants were counted 20 days after inoculation. Virus infection prevention was calculated:

$$\% \text{ prevention} = \frac{\% \text{ infected plants in control} - \% \text{ infected plants in treatment}}{\% \text{ infected plants in control}} \times 100$$

Of granular insecticides tested, carbofuran prevented virus infection at 1 DAT. At 5 DAT it was 89% successful. MIPC, bendiocarb, and BPMC also effectively prevented the virus. All 4 insecticides caused 100% vector mortality.

Although disulfoton, mephosfolan, and phorate also gave 100% vector mortality, they did not prevent tungro virus infection. The remaining granular insecticides

were ineffective in either preventing virus infection or killing the vector.

Acephate (wetable powder [WP]) and carbofuran (foliar) prevented tungro infection 100% at 1 DAT. At 5 DAT, they prevented it 89%. Bendiocarb (WP), carbaryl (WP), and MIPC (WP) also effectively prevented the virus infection.

tion. These 5 insecticides caused 100% vector mortality. DDT (WP) and BHC (WP) neither killed the vector nor prevented virus infection.

Results indicate that insecticides that control the vector do not necessarily prevent virus infection. The reasons are obscure, suggesting that insecticides that prevented infection should be tested in the field. ✎

Effect of granular, wettable powder, and flowable insecticides on rice tungro virus infection and *N. virescens* mortality,^a Cuttack, India.

Insecticide		Prevention of infection (%)		Insect mortality ^b (%)	
Common name	Trade name	1 DAT	5 DAT	1 DAT	5 DAT
Carbofuran	Furadan 3 G	100 a	89 a	100 a	100 a
MIPC	MIPC 4 G	92 b	81 b	100 a	100 a
Bendiocarb	Garvox 5 G	85 b	59 c	100 a	100 a
BPMC	BPMC 4 G	84 b	61 c	100 a	100 a
Thiocyclam hydrogen oxalate	San 155 5 G	55 c	30 d	71 b	38 b
Disulfoton	Solvirex 5 G	34 cd	8 fg	100 a	100 a
Mephosfolan	Cytrolane 5 G	22 de	6 g	100 a	100 a
BHC	Hilbeeche 6 G	12 ef	10 f	24 c	10 c
Diazinon	Diazinon 6 G	8 ef	3 h	69 b	33 b
Quinalphos	Ekalux 5 G	5 fg	3 h	32 c	20 c
Lindane	Lindane 5 G	0 g	9 fg	26 c	17 c
Phorate-1	Phorate 10 G	0 g	0 i	100 a	100 a
Phorate-2	Thimet 10 G	0 g	14 e	100 a	100 a
Acephate	Orthene 75 WP	100 a	89 a	100 a	100 a
Carbofuran	Furadan 40 F	100 a	89 a	100 a	100 a
Bendiocarb	Ficam 80 WP	85 b	84 a	100 a	100 a
Carbaryl	Sevin 50 WP	85 b	84 a	100 a	100 a
MIPC	MIPC 50 WP	85 b	84 a	100 a	100 a
DDT	Hildit 50 WP	35 c	0 b	79 b	13 b
BHC	BHC 50 WP	20 d	0 b	40 c	2 c

^aDAT = days after treatment. Values followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at $P = 0.05$ by Duncan's multiple range test. ^bAdjusted values by Abbott's formula.

Greenhouse evaluation of emulsifiable concentrate insecticides against tungro virus infection

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Twenty-seven emulsifiable concentrate insecticides (see table) were tested in three trials in the nethouse to determine

their ability to prevent tungro virus infection.

Insecticides (0.1% concentration) were sprayed on 35-day-old Taichung Native 1 plants raised in 50 × 40 × 10 cm galvanized trays. Each insecticide treatment had 3 replications of 20 plants each. Each treated plant was inoculated with 2

viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* vectors at 1 and 5 days after treatment (DAT). An equal number of untreated plants were inoculated as control. Insect mortality was recorded 48 hours after caging, and infected plants were counted 20 days after inoculation. Prevention of virus infection was calculated:

$$\% \text{ prevention} = \frac{\% \text{ infected plants in control} - \% \text{ infected plants in treatment}}{\% \text{ infected plants in control}} \times 100$$

Effect of emulsifiable concentrate (EC) insecticides on tungro virus infection and *N. virescens* mortality,^a Cuttack, India.

Insecticide		Prevention of infection (%)		Insect mortality ^b (%)	
Common name	Trade name	1 DAT	5 DAT	1 DAT	5 DAT
Trial 1					
Cypermethrin	Ripcord 10 EC	100 a	100 a	100 a	100 a
DDT	Hildit 25 EC	64 b	32 c	100 a	64 b
Fenitrothion-1	Accothion 50 EC	61 bc	27 c	100 a	70 b
Vamidothion	Vamidothion 30 EC	60 bc	60 b	100 a	100 a
Malathion	Cythion 50 EC	50 c	6 de	100 a	58 b
Phosalone	Zolone 35 EC	37 d	0 e	100 a	100 a
Fenitrothion-2	Folithion 50 EC	19 e	15 cd	72 b	12 c
Methyl parathion	Metacid 50 EC	18 e	20 cd	39 c	7 c
Dichlorvos	Nuvan 100 EC	16 e	12 cd	100 a	100 a
Endosulfan	Hildan 35 EC	1 f	0 e	5 d	3 c
Trial 2					
FMC 35001	Marshall 25 EC	92 a	77 a	100 a	100 a
Ofunack	Ofunack 40 EC	85 a	46 b	100 a	100 a
Monocrotophos	Nuvacon 40 EC	15 b	11 c	97 a	26 b
Dimethoate	Rogor 35 EC	15 b	42 b	65 b	38 b
Formothion	Anthio 25 EC	10 b	6 cd	77 b	11 c
Diazinon	Bazanon 20 EC	9 b	10 cd	80 b	20 bc
Chlorpyrifos	Dursban 20 EC	0 c	0 d	6 c	0 d
Trial 3					
Phosphamidon	Dimecron 40 EC	88 a	61 a	100 a	100 a
Demeton-O-methyl	Metasystox 25 EC	82 a	58 a	100 a	100 a
BPMC	Sulphoxide BPMC 50 EC	62 b	48 ab	88 b	81 b
Quinalphos	Ekalux 25 EC	42 c	22 bc	100 a	53 c
Fenitrothion	Folithion 50 EC	25 d	15 cde	65 c	53 c
Thiometon	Ekatin 25 EC	24 d	7 de	90 a	53 c
Methyl parathion	Paratox 50 EC	17 de	20 bcd	28 d	5 f
Phenthoate-1	Elsan 50 EC	17 de	5 e	89 b	14 e
Carbaryl	Sevimol 40 EC	15 de	8 cde	94 ab	29 d
Phenthoate-2	Phendal50 EC	11 e	6 de	100 a	100 a

^a DAT = days after treatment. Values followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at P = 0.05 by DMRT. ^b Adjusted values by Abbott's formula

Of 10 insecticides tested in trial 1, cypermethrin prevented virus infection at 1 and 5 DAT. Vamidothion provided 60% prevention at 1 and 5 DAT. DDT, fenitrothion-1, and malathion gave some protection at 1 DAT, but little at 5 DAT. Cypermethrin, vamidothion, phosalone, and dichlorvos caused 100% vector mortality at 1 and 5 DAT. DDT, fenitrothion-1, and malathion caused 100% mortality at 1 DAT.

In trial 2, FMC 35001 effectively prevented infection and caused vector mortality. Ofunack was next best. The remaining insecticides neither prevented virus infection nor controlled the vector.

In trial 3 phosphamidon and demeton-O-methyl prevented infection and caused 100% *N. virescens* mortality. Phenthoate-2 controlled the vector at 1 and 5 DAT, but did not prevent infection.

Results indicate that some insecticides that controlled the vector did not prevent virus infection. Phosalone, dichlorvos, and phenthoate-2 killed the vector, but did not prevent infection. This phenomenon needs to be investigated. Cypermethrin, vamidothion, FMC 35001, ofunack, phosphamidon, and demeton-O-methyl prevented virus infection and controlled the vector effectively. ✨

Antagonistic effects of soil microorganisms on rice sheath blight pathogen

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The effects of microorganisms associated with rice sheath blight pathogen on the latter's survival on dryland and wetland culture were investigated.

A *Trichoderma* sp. colonizing the sclerotial bodies of *Thanatephorus*

cucumeris in a dryland rice field was isolated and tested for antagonistic activity against the pathogen. On potato dextrose agar (PDA), an inhibition zone was formed between *Trichoderma* and *T. cucumeris*. Pathogen growth stopped after contact with *Trichoderma*. *Trichoderma* continued growing and eventually covered the whole plate.

Microscopic examination showed that *Trichoderma* frequently coiled around aerial hyphae of *T. cucumeris* on the agar surface. No coiling around subsur-

face hyphae was observed. Scientists observed that: 1) many short branches were produced by the main hyphae of *Trichoderma* and that each branch coiled tightly around the pathogen's hyphae, 2) the main hyphae coiled around the pathogen's hyphae, and the coils formed at a narrower angle with few coils per unit length of hypha, 3) the *Trichoderma* hyphae grew parallel to *T. cucumeris* hyphae and at intervals produced short branches that coiled around the pathogen's hypha. Further examina-